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RESTRUCTURING OF SCHOOL SECURITY IN NORTHERN NIGERIA: THE ROLE OF EDUCATIONAL PSYCHOLOGIST

Hadiza Ahmed Tukur

Department of Educational Psychology, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria

tukurhadiza@gmail.com

Abstract

School security is an approach to safeguard the school from any threat, creating measures and prevention in the school and its environment. The insecurity in Northern Nigeria in the last two decades has been worrisome to all stakeholders. Teaching and learning can only take place in a safe and secured school environment. Education plays significant role in shaping an individual life for laudable social outcomes in the society. This paper discusses urgent need for restructuring of school security in Northern Nigeria. The paper further outlined psychological approaches on the restructuring process that hinges on leading role of education leaders in schools. Similarly, the paper further recommends adequate steps to be taken for effective school security of the region. The study concluded that there should be proper working synergy between the State authorities and educational leaders in the restructuring process and creating awareness of the school security matters.

Keywords: Educational Psychologists, Restructuring, School Security and Teacher

Introduction

With the recent kidnappings in schools across Katsina, Kaduna, Niger and Zamfara States, school security in Northern Nigeria needs to be restructured through leadership actions from the State Governments with the involvement of the school principals and other stakeholders for proper security of staff and students in these schools. The spade of insecurity in Northern Nigeria in the last two decades has been worrisome to all stakeholders. "The region is currently going through a complex mix of security challenges, such as armed banditry and ferocious insurgency of Boko Haram ravaging almost the entire region" (CLEEN Foundation, 2016, p 3). The region is equally confronted with conflicts such as farmers-herders crises, criminal gangs and jihadists (Sabo & Abubakar, 2020). This has affected many communities, businesses, religious organisations and educational institutions. Although government and other stakeholders have adopted different strategies to restore peace to the region, long-lasting peace has not been achieved. Hence, schools which are part of the communities where insecurity has ravaged for decades share in the negative impacts of this dreadful scourge. Several attacks have been recorded in schools with severe injuries to students, destruction of school properties and death of security personnel (Olowoselu, Onuselogu & Obioma, 2015). The schools which are designed to meet the educational needs of the communities in Northern

Nigeria, are presently faced with armed banditry attacks and kidnappings (Dutse & Olowoselu, 2020). Similarly, the security situations within and outside the school environment is currently unfriendly and unsafe for effective teaching and learning to take place. For meaningful teaching and learning to take place, the school environment must be safe, secure and devoid of any traumatic experience and it is worthy of note that a safe school environment is critical to the success of education. Several studies in recent years have however shown that the schools were not so safe for students and the school personnel due to many challenges threatening school security (Fairburn & Grossman, 2006; Schneider, 2008; Alimba, 2018). Likewise, other past studies also reported several attacks on students and teachers in the region. Some of these attacks caused severe injuries to students, destruction of school properties, and death of security personnel (Olowoselu, Onuselogu & Obioma, 2015; Olowoselu, Bello, Onuselogu, 2014).

The experiences of school children in Northern Nigeria have been awful due to the incidents of high-level kidnapping of students in their hundreds from many schools in the region. It has been reported that about 1548 school children and 17 teachers have been kidnapped in about 11 different incidents of mass abduction by terrorists and bandits between 2014 and 2021 (Onuoha & Akogwu, 2022). The security situations within and outside the school environment in Northern Nigeria is currently unfriendly and the rise in the incidents of insecurity in the region is majorly attributed to weak state institutions and isolated nature and weak protective structures around schools in local areas. According to Olugbode (2015), school children now live in apprehension, as they are subjected to emotional trauma due to the level of insecurity around their schools. The spade of insecurity in schools in the region has equally led to death of teachers and students, affected academic achievement and educational goals, reduced students' enrolment and retention and disrupted academic calendar across the region (Muhammed & Ogunode, 2022). Besides, the physical structure of the schools was undoubtedly a crucial challenging issue as many of these schools lack perimeter fences which expose the school to more dangers. In this regard and from the view of a psychologist, the state government and school management, together with the school community have to develop good communication network and security strategies to deal adequately with security issues in the school and its immediate environment.

Concept of Insecurity

Insecurity is a feeling of any form of harm or uncertainty about the wellbeing of an individual. Insecurity undermines the performance of all persons in all areas of life, including the school. Insecurity according to Ubong (2016) occurs whenever people have feeling of self-doubt or feel vulnerable and susceptible to injury or harm for a prolonged period. Insecurity is a sense of vulnerability, defenselessness, lack of protection and danger present in the study area (Sanni, 2015). Any forms of hazard, terror, harassment, unsafe condition in a study area constitute insecurity. In whichever area it manifests itself, insecurity leaves behind ugly experiences on the people and the area it visits. Insecurity undermines the attainment of organizational goals and put the commitment of members of staff in doubt as their wellbeing is in danger. In Northern Nigeria, insecurity is one the major factors militating against the attainment of educational goals as schools. This ugly scenario that has led to the reduction in pupils' enrolment and retention rate has nearly crippled the school system where it manifests. Hence, there is urgent need to restructure school security in Northern Nigeria.

Who should lead Restructuring of School Security?

Psychologically, the researcher is of the opinion that the combination of both education leaders and the help of the security forces should lead the restructuring of school security in their own individual schools with organize communication networks with teachers, security guards in schools, security forces and members of the host community. The education leaders should facilitate weekly school security-council meeting that will serve as medium for sharing security intelligence with the security forces in attendance, members of the traditional council in the host community, hunters and religious leaders in the host community. This will facilitate proper monitoring of security situation, prevention and create effectiveness in school security.

Psychological Impact of Insecurity on Schools in Northern Nigeria

Nothing is good about school insecurity. It disrupts, it hinders, it torments, it traumatises and it breeds negativity everywhere. School insecurity is a burden to students, teachers, school administrators, government, communities and all stakeholders in education. The negative impact of school insecurity according to Muhammed and Ogunode (2022) affects teachers, students, educational objectives, school enrolment and retention, school administration and the academic calendar.

The continuous closure of schools due to the lingering insecurity in Northern Nigeria has put teachers who are the pillar of education off work. While many teachers have been kidnapped (Ogunode, 2021), others have been killed (Ogunode & Atiga, 2021). This has made many professional teachers to either relocate from the region or outrightly abandon the classroom (Muhammad & Ogunode, 2022). Thus, Insecurity puts the lives of teachers in danger, their jobs at risk and their commitments to the teaching profession in doubt.

Students who are at the centre of all educational activities are also negatively affected by the lingering insecurity in schools in Northern Nigeria. Although Schools are principally established to inculcate in the learners' right values, skills and aptitude that will make them useful to themselves and the society at large. Meanwhile, the continuous closure of schools due to incessant abduction of students has threatened the educational objectives (Ogunode & Kolo, 2021) as many students have been kidnapped, killed or displaced. Insecurity in schools in Northern Nigeria has made the learning environment traumatic and not conducive for learning.

According to Ogunode and Kolo (2021), on objective of education, insecurity in schools in Northern Nigeria has led to the poor realization of the objectives of education in the region because insecurity has reduced enrolment and retention rate. Due to high level of insecurity, students' enrolment for most classes has dropped and even those that were previously enrolled in schools sometimes find it difficult to continue as a result of incessant attacks of schools and abductions of students. Similarly, insecurity in Northern Nigeria has led to disruption of school administration as school programmes such as supervision and inspection, teaching and learning, examination and sport activities have been disrupted by insecurity (Muhammed & Ogunode, 2022).

Psychological Approaches on School Security

With the degenerating security situation in schools in Northern Nigeria, many solutions have been suggested to be implemented by different stakeholders. Among such are the provision of adequate security personnel such as police, military and vigilante. The deployment of security guards to schools in Northern Nigeria to curb

insecurity in schools can only be effective if the measure is backed up by intelligence gathering and surveillance to predict potential threat.

The National Association of Psychologists (2018), equally, cautions against over-emphasising armed security in schools as such measures may undermine the learning environment. Combination of measures such as provision of armed security guards, metal detectors and surveillance cameras were recommended and employed in some schools (Cowan, Vaillancourt, Rossen & Pollit, 2013). Just as many school administrators and stakeholders have deployed these measures and many others, Oguzie (2014) advocated the use of guidance and counselling services as a strategy for imbuing the consciousness of long-lasting peace, conflict resolution and national security. Guidance and counselling services will be a strong tool for achieving the needed peace in the region due to its ability to appeals to and convinces the conscience of individuals and groups involve in creating insecurity in the region. Similarly, Alimba (2018) opined that security of schools involves creating awareness and enlightenment about security issues and prevention in school environments. While, Ozmenam, Durb and Akgulc (2010) asserted that all school principals should develop emergency action plans to curb any threat to the school environment. This will be achieved with proper communication channel to all staff and students in the school on what to be done in emergency situations. Alimba (2018) further stressed that there is the need for school principals' and teachers to acquire security skills and knowledge on how to manage security issues and when to react to certain security threats that may occur in their school environments. Even though, Dutse and Olowoselu (2020) posits that the State Governments have the sole responsibility to protect life and properties of every individual in the society. Fervently, it is the duty of every individual to also contribute in providing adequate information to security forces for prompt action. Drawing upon the above statements and the need for safe school environment, the researcher posits that school security improvements should be all stakeholders' affair that involves prudent participation from all individuals in the society, with higher level of commitments and expectations roles from the education leaders and school host and community members.

Conversely, it is important to ascertain that, school should organise workshop on security education that encompasses crime prevention, security safety skills and strategies to all staff in the schools. The process will improve teachers' security consciousness in the school and community. Alimba (2018) posited aims of security education as proactive responses to security threats in school and community, and to expose school staff to the existing security laws. More so, security education will enhance the school staff to be able to classify and categorise threats as either internal or external threat to the school and more importantly, it will stimulate the school staff to take adequate measures to react to threat for self-prevention and prevention of others in the school.

Role of Education Leaders in Restructuring the School Security

Assuredly, from the psychological perspectives, the researcher posited the following as effective ways of restructuring the school security in Northern Nigeria:

Planning –The education leaders should make a detailed plan of the school security vision and mission that will gear up effective communication link to all teachers, students, parents and other stakeholders during emergency. Meanwhile, a quick response model should be adopted during any emergency in the school.

Sense of urgency – All education leaders should ensure proper contact with security forces attached to the host community for immediate response to emergency or treat on the school. The education leaders should communicate clearly to school staff on new patterns and development on security exigencies in the community with effect on new measures and actions to curb it.

Stakeholders – There should be high level security support, collaboration and exchange of information from education leaders to teachers and other school non- teaching staff, community members and parents in enhancing safe and secured school in the community.

Leadership Focus –The State authority, the security forces and education leaders are in the leadership positions to implement the restructuring of school security in Northern Nigeria. This is achievable through clear safe school vision and mission, commitment, consistent and follow-up with great focus on the safe school initiatives.

Effect on Results –Measuring school security successes and regular training of school staff will have significant impact on school security and improvement on safe school initiatives. Capacity development of school security personnel and the collaboration of community vigilante members with the Nigerian Police Force will improve security of life and properties in schools.

Recommendations

The researchers made the following recommendations to be considered when restructuring of school security in Northern Nigeria:

- a. School emergency communication database should be set-up to communicate with the necessary security units and organizations to receive timely help and support in threatening situations.
- b. All school staff should be trained on school security prevention and management strategies.
- c. School security committee should be set up in each school which composed of the school principal, teachers, students, parents, members of host community and security organizations.
- d. There should be an ACT of National Assembly legislations on school security so as to provide security to schools in Nigeria.
- e. The perimeter fencing of schools is mandatory with fence protectors and close circuit cameras with night vision should be placed inside and outside the school buildings.
- f. The school environment should be closely watched with the cooperation of all security officials, any suspicious threat to the school environment should be reported to security agencies.
- g. Extra-curriculum activities should be enhanced so as to make the students use their leisure time well and develop sound academic attitude towards one another in the school.
- h. Finally, in ensuring safe and secure school environment, the schools should develop school-based prevention and response strategies to deal effectively with any threat both internally or externally to the schools.

Conclusion

To educational psychologists, it is believed that teaching and learning can only take place in a safe and secure school environment. The study discusses the prompt need for restructuring of school security in Northern Nigeria. The rationale behind this study was based on the need for all stakeholders and education leaders to map out

plans on the restructuring of school security. Likewise, the study further affirmed the leading role of education leaders in the restructuring of school security. Therefore, it is very crucial for State authorities to develop a synergy with the education leaders in the restructuring process of school security in Nigeria at large.

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